

METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF ASSESSING THE FINANCIAL SECURITY OF ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

The world's leading international organizations and research institutes, such as the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, and the UN, are conducting scientific research in the areas of mitigating the effects of global warming, introducing innovations in the construction industry, increasing the volume of net assets, capitalization in the stock market, and risk management in enterprises.

The world's leading international organizations and research institutes, such as the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, and the UN, are conducting scientific research in the areas of mitigating the effects of global warming, introducing innovations in the construction industry, increasing the volume of net assets, capitalization in the stock market, and risk management in enterprises. As a result of these studies, strategies for adapting to a changing environment have been proposed, and measures have been developed to reduce the impact of external threats and economic sanctions on the construction industry. However, the issues of ensuring the financial security of construction industry enterprises remain relevant.

Among the scientists who have most clarified the concept of "financial security" is V.I. Senchagov in his scientific views defines "financial security as the development of the financial system and ensuring financial relations and processes in the economy, in which the necessary financial conditions are created for the socio-economic and financial stability of the country's development" as "the state of the economy from the point of view of its ability to survive in conditions of internal and external threats, as well as the difficulty of working in an unpredictable environment and predicting factors".

The works of the above-mentioned authors undoubtedly make a great contribution to the theory of ensuring the financial security of an enterprise. However, due to the complexity and multifacetedness of the problem of ensuring the financial security of an enterprise, not all its aspects have been sufficiently studied in these studies. There is a need to scientifically substantiate the use of generally accepted management methods in order to ensure and assess the financial security of enterprises, adapt the experience of foreign countries to the conditions of Uzbekistan, and develop a methodology for ensuring the financial security of enterprises in accordance with the needs of our country's enterprises.

Financial security of the enterprise is the degree of protection against the negative effects of external and internal threats in a certain period of time, which ensures the stable implementation of the enterprise's financial interests and strategic goals.

Thus, "financial stability of the enterprise is the main part of the financial security of the enterprise, its determining factor". After all, it is possible to ensure the financial security of enterprises only through the stable development of the enterprise. For this, it is necessary to create conditions in enterprises that can adapt to changes in the internal and external environment.

According to the author, the financial security of the enterprise is a state of protection against internal and external threats that threaten the financial stability of the enterprise and may arise in the future.

This methodology is absolutely not suitable for assessing the current state of financial security of building materials enterprises. Various mathematical and economic models have been developed. The most famous and significant of them are described in the works of economists E. Altman, R. Taffler, G. Tishou, V. Beaver, J. Konnan, M. Golder, G. Stringate, D. Fulmer, R. Lees, A. Strickland, J. Olson.

The causes of crises, their types, consequences, and the processes of forming anti-crisis strategies are very well covered. A. Thompson, J. Richard, Z. Helfert, R. Holt, and others have dealt with these issues. Russian scientists R.S. Saifullin and G.G. Kadikov tried to adapt E. Altman's "Z-score" model to Russian conditions. New methods for diagnosing possible bankruptcy for local enterprises were developed by O.P. Zaitseva, R.S. Saifullin and G. G. Kadikov.

Well-known models for diagnosing bankruptcy of enterprises are also not suitable for assessing the current state of financial security of building materials enterprises: the coefficients are not suitable due to the characteristics of the country's economy; local building materials enterprises show weak activity in the stock market; they are based only on financial statements.

The fact that the database is based only on financial statements in diagnosing bankruptcy shows the past state of the enterprise (since it is based on quarterly or annual reports), does not fully predict future threats.

First of all, at the first stage it is necessary to select a system of indicators that will open up opportunities for assessing the financial security of the enterprise. This structure of functional components corresponds to the structure of the mechanism for ensuring the financial security of the enterprise and affects all functional areas of the enterprise's activity: innovations, resources, investments, marketing, their goals should correspond to the strategic interests of the enterprise.

During the study, an algorithm for conducting financial analysis of enterprises of the building materials industry was proposed (Fig. 1).

The basis for a comprehensive analysis of the financial condition is the analysis of the organization's financial statements. Accounting analysis is a process that assesses the past and current state of the organization's activities.

The results of the analysis of financial statements are used to identify problems in the management of production and commercial activities, select areas for capital investment,

evaluate the activities of the organization's management, as well as forecast its individual indicators and financial indicators. Analysis of the financial condition is the basis for developing the enterprise's financial policy.

The country is moving towards industrialization of the economy, improvement of living standards, and modernization of society. As a result, in the last 4 years, the GDP growth rate has reached almost 6% per year, which indicates that the market's political and economic situation is improving and a stable development situation is forming.

International indices help to assess the level of political stability in a country. In particular, the World Bank annually publishes the Governance Index (WGI). The index covers 200 countries and is based on six sub-indexes: political stability and the absence of violence, the quality of regulation, the rule of law, accountability of government to the people, government efficiency, and control over corruption. According to the World Bank, over the past decade, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been among the lagging countries. However, taking into account the current reforms and innovations, the level of political stability can be considered satisfactory and has prospects for improvement.

When assessing the impact of the external environment on the level of financial security of enterprises in the building materials industry, 5 experts with more than 10 years of experience in the industry are interviewed, the arithmetic average of their assessments is taken and rounded to the nearest whole.

The list of criteria is filled in by an odd-numbered group of experts, taking into account the development of the industry and its specific characteristics. Top managers can use this questionnaire themselves or give it to the relevant specialists for filling in.

Having determined the values of the parameters related to the financial security of enterprises in the building materials industry in the external environment, we calculate the cumulative coefficient of the external and internal environment:

$$K_{fin.sec.} = (R_{int.}^{over} + R_{ext.}^{over})/2$$

$R_{ext.}^{over}$ – the average rating of experts placed on the external environment;

$R_{int.}^{over}$ – the average rating of experts placed on the internal environment.

The determined result is between 24 and 120 points, the higher the result, the higher the financial security of the building materials industry enterprise.

After calculating the cumulative indicator, it is necessary to evaluate it on the appropriate scale to analyze the level of financial security of the enterprise.

The overall activity of the enterprise belongs to the medium security zone. This means that the company primarily has problems related to the modernization of products and technologies. These are the main issues, without which the enterprise cannot maintain its competitiveness and security. Financial indicators are in the medium zone. These indicators reflect the content of the financial stability and profitability of the enterprise, they are calculated on the basis of financial reporting data and should be more closely controlled by the enterprise management. Production indicators associated with the high security zone indicate the best situation. However, it should be noted that all indicators of economic activity are interconnected, and the state of indicators close to the crisis zone indicates a possible deterioration in other indicators, including production indicators. Based on the results obtained, a program of measures to increase the level of economic security of the enterprise is

developed, which corresponds to the final stage of security management. Increasing the economic security of the enterprise should be carried out step by step, the potential indicators should be transferred from a lower level to a higher one by developing and implementing an enterprise development program over a certain period..

References:

- 1.Senchagov V.K. Economic Security of Russia. General Course [Electronic resource]: textbook / edited by V.K. Senchagov. - 5th ed. (el.). - Electronic text data. (1 pdf file: 818 p.). - Moscow: BINOM. Laboratory of Analysis, 2015. 269 bet.
 - 2.Senchagov V.I. On the Essence and Foundations of Russia's Economic Security Strategy // Voprosy ekonomiki. 1995. No. 1. P. 98
 - 3.Unkovskaya T.E. A New Paradigm for Understanding Financial Stability / T.E. Unkovskaya // Economic Theory. 2009. No. 1. P. 12-13
- B. Tursunov. Improving the methodology for ensuring the financial security of enterprises. Abstract. Tashkent - 2021.

